

The Use of Leucotrope as a Benzylating Agent.

BY

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Leucotrope (phenylbenzyl dimethyl ammonium chloride) has been used for some time commercially as a benzylating agent (*cf.* D. R. P. 184381 and 231543). Tschugaeff and Chlopin (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1272) used it for the preparation of dibenzyl telluride. In the present paper an account is given of its application to the benzylation of phenols and also of a similar application of *para*- and *meta*-nitroleucotropes; the nitroleucotropes have already been applied in the production of the nitrobenzyl ethers of cellulose (Peacock, *Indian Patent*, Appn. No. 11548 of 1925).

Leucotrope was prepared by Michler and Gradmann (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 2079) by the direct combination of dimethyl aniline and benzyl chloride. *p*-Nitrobenzylphenyldimethyl ammonium chloride was prepared in a similar way from *p*-nitrobenzyl chloride by Wedekind (*Annalen*, 1899, 307, 287).

m-Nitrobenzyl chloride combines with dimethyl aniline more readily than the *para* compound (*cf.* Peacock, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2179), and gives *m*-nitrobenzylphenyldimethyl ammonium chloride.

In the earlier experiments the phenol was dissolved in aqueous caustic soda solution but it was later found that this was unnecessary and that benzylation proceeds quite smoothly in the presence of sodium carbonate. The benzylation of the nitrophenols proceeds much less

readily than does that of phenol. Salicylic acid was recovered unchanged from an attempt at benzylation.

Phenylbenzyl ether, was first prepared by Sintenin (*Annalen*, 1867, 143, 81). The *ortho*- and *para*-nitrophenyl benzyl ethers and the *ortho*- and *para*-nitrobenzylphenyl ethers were prepared by Kump (*Annalen*, 1884, 224, 104) by the action of the corresponding benzyl chloride upon the potassium salt of the corresponding phenol in alcoholic solution. Staedel (*Annalen*, 1883, 217, 44) in a similar way prepared the benzyl ethers of the cresols and of α - and β -naphthols. Sintenin (*Annalen*, 1872, 161, 345) obtained a chlorophenylbenzyl ether of m. p. 70-71°, by the chlorination of phenylbenzyl ether in the presence of mercuric oxide. He did not determine the constitution of this compound: I find that the melting point of *p*-chlorophenylbenzyl ether is 71°. Sintenin's compound therefore, is the *para* isomeride. The *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chlorophenylbenzyl ethers and the 2 : 4-dichlorophenylbenzyl ether seem to be new substances.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenylbenzyl dimethyl ammonium chloride, *p*-nitrobenzylphenyldimethyl ammonium chloride and *m*-nitrobenzylphenyldimethyl ammonium chloride were prepared in the usual manner. *m*-Nitrobenzylphenyl dimethyl ammonium chloride is new; m. p. 144°. (Found: Cl = 12.93. $C_{15}H_{17}N_2O_2Cl$ requires Cl = 12.13 per cent.)

The general method employed for benzylation can be illustrated by two examples.

α -Naphthyl benzyl ether.

α -Naphthol (7.3 g.) and benzylphenyldimethyl ammonium chloride (6.15 g.) in sodium carbonate solution (7 g. in 100 c.c.) were heated under a reflux condenser

for 4 hours. The mixture having been extracted with benzene, the extract was washed with caustic soda to remove naphthol and then with hydrochloric acid (1:1) to remove dimethylaniline. The extract was then dried over calcium chloride: after removal of the benzene the residue solidified to a mass of brownish crystals which when crystallized from alcohol formed colourless crystals, m. p. 74.5° - 76° ; Braun and Reich (*Annalen*, 1925, 445, 233) give the m. p. 61° . The yield of crude substance was 5 g. (Found: C=86.94; H=6.72. $C_{17}H_{14}O$ requires C=87.12; H=5.98 per cent.) The molecular weight determined by the depression of the freezing point was 240; calculated 234. Stadel (*loc. cit.*) obtained this compound as an oil.

Phenyl-p-nitrobenzyl ether.

Phenol (4.7 g.) and *p*-nitrobenzyl phenyldimethyl ammonium chloride (14.6 g.) were mixed with excess of caustic soda (15 c.c. of 4*N* caustic soda diluted to 50 c.c., and the mixture was heated under a reflux condenser for four hours. The mixture having been extracted with benzene was washed with caustic soda to remove unchanged phenol, then with hydrochloric acid (1:1) and finally with water. The benzene extract was then dried over calcium chloride. After removal of the benzene the residue, which was solid, was crystallized from alcohol; m. p. 91° . Kump (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 91° .

Phenylbenzyl ether prepared in a similar manner had the m. p. 39° . Sintenin (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 38° - 39° .

Benzyl-*o*-cresyl ether, b. p. 284° ; Stadel (*loc. cit.*) gives b. p. 285° - 290° . Benzyl-*m*-cresyl ether, m. p. 43° ; Stadel (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 43° . Benzyl-*p*-cresyl ether, m. p. 40° ; Stadel (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 41° . Benzyl- β -naphthyl ether m. p. 99° - 100° , Stadel (*loc. cit.*) gives

m. p. 99°. *Benzyl-o-chlorophenyl ether*, m. p. 296°. (Found: Cl=16.06; $C_{13}H_{11}OCl$ requires Cl=16.24 per cent.) *Benzyl-m-chlorophenyl ether*, colourless crystals from alcohol, m. p. 59°. (Found: Cl=16.6 per cent.) *Benzyl-p-chlorophenyl ether*, colourless crystals from alcohol; m. p. 71°. (Found: Cl=16.59). *Benzyl-2:4-dichlorophenyl ether*, colourless crystals from alcohol; m. p. 60°. (Found: Cl=27.85. $C_{13}H_{10}OCl_2$ requires Cl=27.78 per cent.) *p*-Nitrobenzylphenyl ether, m. p. 91°; Kump (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 91°. *Benzyl-p-nitrophenyl ether*, m. p. 106° (the yield was very small); Kump (*loc. cit.*) gives m. p. 106°.

Further experiments are in progress with other hydroxy substances, including celluloses, and with amines.

I wish to thank Professor D. H. Peacock for suggesting this work and for advice during its progress.

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Received, December 26, 1925.
